

Challenges in Industry 5.0: Human behavior integration

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Abstract. This paper aims to contribute to facilitate the contribution of people to production processes by promoting an integrative framework promoting collecting specific and helpful data from the workers impacting in the process but also to facilitate data integration with process data. For industrial processes these aspects are significantly challenging because that integration must happen in multi-tenant environments and human behaviors are affected by time dependent factors such as tiredness, stress, work overload, etc. To deal with these constraints, the technology involved for human data collection requires particular attention, allowing to facilitate not just understanding about the process syntaxis but also the semantic interpretation. Therefore, this paper will deeply describe some of the involved implementation details.

Keywords: Industry 5.0, Human monitoring, Ontologies, Mobile wearable monitoring.

1 Introduction

Process plants now commonly store extensive historical data in databases. These databases are populated by continuously collecting data from numerous online sensors, monitoring hundreds to thousands of variables every few seconds. Leveraging this data is a critical aspect of ensuring the long-term success of industrial processes. These datasets are typically vast in size, with high levels of correlation among variables (many of which are collinear) and lacking causal relationships [1, 2]. The information contained in any single variable is often quite limited due to low signal-to-noise ratios, and there are frequently missing measurements for various variables [3]. However, to obtain benefits from such datasets, different issues must be addressed.

First, until about a decade ago, very little had been done with this data, primarily due to its inherent characteristics. Nowadays, because of the improvements induced by the Industry 4.0 paradigm (I4.0) allowed to create models developed by using latent variable methods such as principal component analysis (PCA) and other projection techniques such as projection to latent structures (PLS) among others [4]. I4.0

allows to systematically address their analysis in a straightforward manner and provide analysis tools that are easy to present and interpret.

Second, when examining the information derived from the gathered data, distinct interests come into play. On one hand, there is a focus on monitoring the process itself, while on the other hand, the emphasis is placed on specific quality aspects of the products. In both scenarios, but particularly in the former, there is a tendency to rely on traditional Statistical Process Control techniques (SPC) [5, 6], even though these techniques are grounded in the assumption of unidimensional variable behavior, whereas the actual situation aligns more closely with multivariate behavior [7]. Indeed, causality relationships between product quality issues and process monitoring have been pursued by using different type of modelling strategies [7–9]. However, these relationships are mediated by several factors which affect the efficiency of the approached, such as variable time span between the processes data and the product being impacted, difficulties in stablishing relationships between the product ids and the different process status at the different machines for that product.

Finally, but importantly, the hardest limitation for many processes is the variability induced by the human factor into the interested relationships [10]. This is because human related variables have been not commonly recorded and, therefore, the reconstruction of the product flow through the different processes and their transitions becomes extremely limited when human intervention is required [10, 11].

By exclusively focusing on quality variables (Statistical Quality Control or SQC), we tend to overlook the multitude of process variables that are measured much more frequently than the data related to product quality. Monitoring these process variables is anticipated to yield a wealth of information about the process's condition, and this information is available at a higher frequency. Additionally, any unusual events that occur will also leave traces within the process data. Therefore, once an abnormal situation is detected, it becomes easier to pinpoint the source of the problem because we are directly examining the process variables.

In contrast, control charts that solely focus on product variables only indicate a deviation from specifications in product characteristics, without identifying the specific process variables responsible for this deviation. Unfortunately, when the influence comes from the human mediation by action or omission these effects cannot be considered because they are not registered.

Therefore, to contribute to the reduction of variability for process and to increase consistency and transparency for those processes, it becomes necessary to integrate relevant information from workers. In this way there are several research questions to be addressed,

RQ1: Is there a convenient IT architecture able to collect mobile information related to workers linked to the interesting processes?

RQ2: Does the proposed architecture bring capabilities to estimate tiredness during a whole shift?

RQ3: Can such information be referred in a convenient semantic way easing its integration with other information related to the sensors inside the process?

Hereinafter the paper will be structured as follows. First, a literature review section is presented. The next section looks to introduce the proposed framework enabling to

describe the contribution of the people through wearable sensors. The fourth section will apply the proposed framework to specific wearable sensors and finally the last section will discuss the conclusions.

2 State of the Art

Since the topics being addressed are related to Industry 5.0, infrastructure for monitoring mobile wearables as well as data integration, specific section devoted to each of them is proposed.

2.1 Infrastructure for monitoring wearables

In recent times, wearable devices have garnered significant attention and widespread adoption, thanks to their compact size, adequate computing capabilities, and practical power efficiency. These wearable gadgets, equipped with sensors like accelerometers and gyroscopes, present a promising option for tracking users' everyday activities, such as walking, jogging, and even behaviors like smoking [12, 13]. Nowadays wearable devices find applications in various domains, with health monitoring being a notable and prominent one, particularly in the context of activity detection [14].

The increasing utility of wearable sensor devices in delivering precise and dependable insights into individuals' activities and behaviors has prompted a considerable amount of ongoing research. This research is focused on the development of smart sensing systems designed to monitor human activities effectively [15]. Nonetheless, wearable technology encounters four primary challenges that need to be addressed: communication capacity, security, computational power, and the limited energy capacity of the wearable device [16, 17].

Some of these challenges are interconnected. For example, limitations in available energy and the size of wearables can impact communication capacity and security stack protocols. However, recent research introduces various approaches that deserve specific attention. One such approach is the Internet of Wearable Things (IoWT), which falls under the broader concept of the Internet of Things (IoT). IoWT pertains to portable personal devices equipped with self-contained sensing, energy, computing, and communication components in a compact to microscopic form. These devices can establish wireless peer-to-peer communication with one another or connect to a personal hub like a smartphone, enabling access to the Internet [18–20].

Wearable devices are on the rise in popularity due to their wide-ranging applications. Smartwatches gather a diverse array of personal data. While these devices offer convenience to consumers, they also introduce additional security concerns, including potential cybersecurity risks, device penetration, and the exploitation of vulnerabilities. Wearable devices are susceptible to attacks, and hacking could expose the collected data. Issues such as insufficient authentication, location tracking, Bluetooth vulnerabilities, and security gaps are all inherent challenges with these devices. Despite the presence of security guidelines for such devices, consumers are often unaware of the associated risks [21]. Hence, a major challenge for researchers and devel-

opers is to ensure the security triangle of CIA (Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability) for individuals [22].

Due to constraints on energy availability and the necessary sampling frequency for monitored data, edge computing capabilities are often restricted. To address this challenge, one approach is to conduct certain computations at the local hub and distribute data across multiple cloud platforms, primarily driven by the involvement of diverse devices [23]. Advocating for the extension of cloud capabilities in proximity to mobile and IoT devices appears to be a feasible model that can also be implemented in work environments, as exemplified in [20], with the aim of advancing an Operator 4.0 architectural framework.

The communication limitations exhibited by wearable devices forced developers to rely on personal hubs, with different devices linked by Bluetooth protocol to the smartphone [24, 25]. Nonetheless, advanced 6G technologies, engineered to support cellular IoT connections and services like long-range low-power communication (LRLPC), ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC), and in-network intelligent computing services (INICS), have been found to align effectively with the needs of IoWT [25].

2.2 Data integration

Human factors, such as indicators of fatigue, exert substantial influence on both product quality as well as factory productivity within manufacturing operations. It is evident that enhancing the integration of data, including information from wearables, can enhance our comprehension of business performance. Indeed, when the goal is to augment existing information, achieving a more robust level of data integration that encompasses both sub-systems (process and operator) becomes essential for establishing an effective and efficient human-cyber-physical partnership [26, 27].

Consequently, pervasive data interconnectivity and data-driven dynamic decision-making represent pivotal elements in the infrastructure of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) to deliver a substantial boost in overall business performance [28]. Because of the demand for data connectivity and the presence of multiple cloud platforms, a requisite emerges for data consolidation from dispersed sources, a task that the framework must address to render the data valuable.

An improved version of the LASFA architecture [29] has been proposed in [28] and named LASFA+. This enhanced architecture offers a broader outlook on the components involved in production. It goes beyond traditional assets and includes extended ones, offering supplementary insights into the production process. Some of these services are dependent on either local or, more commonly, provider-based clouds located outside the company's scope. Consequently, the reference model must align with these practical conditions.

Another distinction lies in the roles of Manufacturing Execution System (MES) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, with MES traditionally positioned closer to production and serving as a means of visualizing production process data. Machines, devices, and individuals are equipped with sensors to facilitate interconnection and communication.

The proposed architecture enables the connectivity of individuals through affordable wearable devices that are readily accessible in the market, such as personal health-tracking devices. This framework enables the gathering of not only physical attributes and events but also virtual ones, which are generated by the model's output. This capability becomes particularly valuable when integrated to create more complex models.

To enhance data interoperability, semantic information is included in each data message within this architecture. This approach enables the utilization of pre-existing ontologies across various domains, extending beyond the industrial sector. Structured data, grounded in these ontologies, can be seamlessly integrated into other datasets, thereby enriching the functionality of advanced applications, including data-driven AI algorithms. Furthermore, ontologies that align with existing ones or are newly introduced serve a supportive role within this semantic modeling module.

2.3 Industry 5.0

In the past, most data integration initiatives predominantly focused on managing data from databases. However, contemporary approaches promote the inclusion of both structured and unstructured data. While there are numerous existing and emerging standards for corporate data interchange, many of them have been developed using diverse methodologies and without taking compatibility with other standards into account, regardless of whether they are used within the same or different contexts. There has been a lack of a global strategy to ensure interoperability among these standards, mainly because they were initially created independently [30].

Some authors, such as [31] have proposed principles and a list of requirements trying to address shortcomings related to these limitations, such as the “usage of a common data model”, but “providing different ways of data processing” “having support from a variety of tools”. All these principles must be compatible with “privacy and security of the data” in a context of “making data transparently available”, as the convenient approach to provide consistent and robust data integration configuration.

The rapid proliferation of consumer-grade wearable devices in today's ever-evolving technology landscape has created a situation where there is limited comprehension of how these devices perform under similar conditions. Moreover, there is a dearth of guidance available to researchers across various fields who are in the process of designing new studies aimed at assessing and choosing technologies that align with their study objectives, target population, and overall context. Hence, there is a pressing need for a systematic and expeditious process to evaluate and select commercial wearable devices that can effectively meet the requirements of their research projects. This evaluation should not only consider the devices in isolation but also consider the data integration principles mentioned earlier.

Industry 5.0 has data interoperability as one of its core principles [32], the efficient usage requires not just syntactic interoperability but semantic and organizational ones. In the past, application architects often overlooked the crucial aspect of ensuring transparent and readily accessible data while simultaneously maintaining a unified model and offering diverse data processing options. This led to the development of

constrained services where data integration primarily focused on syntax. To achieve comprehensive semantic and operational interoperability across various tools and processes, it is imperative to preserve the entire data flow. This can be accomplished by utilizing convenient ontology resources for semantic description, while data privacy and security are typically safeguarded by the IT infrastructure through various mechanisms, including VPN access and the issuance of limited-time tokens [33].

Interconnection models are essential components within the overarching reference framework. This implies that standard networking topologies, such as wearables-to-hub (W2H) and wearables-to-infrastructure (W2I) architectures, have their own significance and must seamlessly integrate into the overarching framework. Although it is a requirement for data interoperability, it needs to accommodate verification of principles for data integration as well.

3 Proposed Framework

As previously discussed, there is a demand for a more comprehensive conceptualization of wearable data in the intricate semantic context of industrial processes. This is particularly important when it comes to interactions between discrete equipment states and human operators, aiming to minimize variations in comprehending the entire process flow.

Fig. 1. Schema for the proposed framework.

From the review of current practices, we have discerned that despite the numerous frameworks put forth, there are ongoing requirements concerning multi-cloud architectures that cater to various types of wearable devices, all while facilitating the semantic definition of data flows using the appropriate ontology. Furthermore, the need for versatility to perform computations both at the edge and within the cloud infrastructure remains imperative.

The framework under consideration in **Fig. 1** advocates for the comprehensive management of human data flow, integrating it with other data flows related to processes, machinery, and/or products, with a primary emphasis on human-related information.

It enables the concurrent operation of various wearable devices, reflecting a prevalent trend in the current landscape. This encompasses not only wearables on the human body but also those collecting data from the vehicles (e.g., forklift, car, or truck) that workers use in supply chain operations. Consequently, multiple physical layers are anticipated, where all pertinent data converge at a personal hub. This hub is responsible for preliminary data processing and subsequent submission to the relevant cloud platform, contingent on the device manufacturer or the specific data collection application employed.

The next pivotal element involves the development of the ontology in accordance with the data source. This necessitates careful attention to establishing sufficient connections between entities to adequately define them and facilitate interactions between them. This approach allows for the federation of entities and ontologies, facilitating the creation of an attribute network. The specific nature of these relationships will depend on the case being analyzed, and as such, they may not be identifiable at the point of initial cloud data injection but may become apparent in subsequent stages.

Operating in a manner consistent with other significant data flows, such as those related to processes, machinery, and products, the integrative layer will establish valuable connections between the participating entities. This will be achieved through the application of relevant properties, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of machinery operations in conjunction with the actions of workers within specific process pathways. As a result, a deeper level of observation becomes attainable, reducing uncertainty. Consequently, it becomes possible to construct models with enhanced explanatory capacity [34, 35]. In certain instances, direct observation of specific entities holds inherent significance, either independently or in collaboration with the outcomes of the models.

4 Application Case

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the provided framework, we have implemented it within an industrial setting that combines both automated and manual elements in a manufacturing process. The specific case pertains to an industrial process within the automotive industry, involving the production of a cross car beam. This process encompasses a substantial level of robotic involvement, primarily for part inspection,

with some sections requiring manual manufacturing and transportation based on the process logic.

To assess operational scenarios for processes, such as identifying the need for re-manufacturing or determining acceptance and delivery, simply understanding the product identities, inspection codes, machines, and operations is insufficient. It is essential to incorporate human behavior observations, including position monitoring and monitoring of fatigue during the operational phase. This is necessary because fatigue can impact response times and the duration of various tasks.

In this application, a variety of wearables were employed, including an Ultra Wide Band (UWB) tag for position tracking, an accelerometer to measure the angle of the arm in relation to the vertical, and smart socks to monitor walking style. These data streams facilitated the identification of workers involved in specific tasks based on their positions and the times at which they were active. Additionally, fatigue levels were inferred from the duration of time spent with the arm at a specific angle and from changes in walking style over time, including trajectory. This comprehensive approach significantly reduces variability attributed to human behavior, enabling the precise identification of contributors at the item level within the process.

The different devices in use have been those presented in **Fig. 2**, connected with the needs already described. In all the cases wearable battery last longer than a shift, which enable the longitudinal monitoring of each signal independently.

Fig. 2. Type of wearable devices selected for the application case. Left: the UWB tag with enclosure linked to the worker helmet. Center: accelerometer monitoring the arm angle. Right: The smart socks monitoring the walking steps carried out by the worker.

The choice between using the wearable provider's cloud solution for tracking and monitoring or designing a specific app (for arm angle and smart socks) with a local cloud alternative depended on the specific application case. The decision was influenced by factors such as the sampling frequency provided and the ease of accessing information through the API-REST solution.

To avoid excessive details, we are describing the process followed with one type of wearable, such as the smart socks, because it illustrates well the trade-off required. On one side the sampling frequency was fixed as a minimum of 25Hz for all the variables (Foot pressures, accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer), meaning 12 variables in total as cartesian components are collected. The final sampling frequency was 40Hz, looking to better describe the step characteristics, that means more than one hundred thousand samples per worker, variable and shift.

An Android based app has been created [36] to collect the relevant information, as part of the personal hub layer described in the proposed framework. At such layer data preparation and compression is performed before uploading to the private cloud. At the same layer the industrial provider uploads worker position by interpolating distances between the base stations at fixes places and such data are uploaded into its cloud. A sample overview of the collected data can be obtained through a Grafana service connected to the cloud, as presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Small time window of the uploaded data showing the steps on each leg in terms of pressure, acceleration, gyroscope and Magnetometer.

In the context of this industrial scenario, various ontologies were selected for data modeling to map the generated data sources. The criteria for selecting these ontologies were based on how closely the ontological schema matched the structure of the data sources. After deeper analysis of each ontology's schema, as listed in **Table 1**, the fuzzy ontologies solution [37] have been used to model walking characteristics; the arm position was described by using [38]; the worker's position has been represented using the positioning ontology [39] while the PLM (Product Lifecycle Management) ontology [40].

Table 1. Ontology reusability selection.

Indoor Positioning System	Wearable	Production System
Positioning Ontology [39]	MIMU-Wear Ontology [38]	MES ontology [41]
Indoor GML [42]	HealthIoT Ontology [43]	PLM Ontology [40]
Navigation Ontology [39, 44]	Fuzzy ontologies [37]	

Leveraging existing methodologies and the mapping tool Karma, which offers a graphical user interface, automates the process of semantic modeling. You can find more information about Karma at <https://usc-isi-i2.github.io/karma/> [45]. Karma possesses the ability to autonomously learn how data maps to selected ontology classes, enabling it to suggest a model for generating JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data (JSON-LD) from large datasets in batch mode. JSON-LD is a lightweight Linked Data format that was specifically designed with the concept of 'context' in mind. It establishes connections between object properties in JSON and concepts within an ontology. JSON-LD was chosen due to its lightweight characteristics and its capability to function at a web-scale while providing embedded semantics.

This data format, which builds upon JSON and ontological schemas, serves to establish a shared understanding and facilitates the adaptation of schemas over time without requiring alterations for data consumers. The key components involved encompass the data source, the utilized ontology schema, and the resultant transformed JSON-LD format, enriched with semantic annotations.

The pending aspect to be handled from the research questions is the one related to tiredness, and to address it, low level data analysis was carried out at the beginning of the shift and at the end of it, by using Fast Fourier Transformation of the signals (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Sample size used for the FFT analysis

In order to be consistent with the physics of the movement, it was decided that individual coordinate axes were less relevant than the modulus variation for gyroscope

and acceleration, and then all these signal were transformed to the frequency domain, as presented in **Fig 5**.

Fig. 5. FFT analysis of signals. On x axis the frequency in Hz, the vertical axis is the normalized amplitude. The first row represents the modulus of the gyroscope signals on each leg, the

second row represents the modulus of the acceleration, and the next three rows represent the pressure on the heel and on other two places closed to foot fingers.

The observed frequency for steps of this worker was 1.25Hz (0.8s) consistently from the gyroscope, accelerometer as well as from the pressure sensors. When the analysis is repeated few hours later, close to the end of the shift, a similar behavior is found, but now the frequency found is around 1Hz (1s), which is 25% slower than at the beginning.

5 Conclusions

The paper introduces a framework for the holistic management of human data flow, allowing seamless integration with other data streams associated with processes, machinery, and products, placing a significant emphasis on data related to human activities. This framework is adaptable and accommodates various wearable devices operating within a personal hub layer equipped with edge computing capabilities, facilitating the transfer of data to the relevant cloud system.

Through a federated approach, this data is enriched to imbue it with semantic context, making it ready for integration at a level equivalent to that of conventional data streams.

With this framework in place, it becomes feasible to provide affirmative responses to both the first and third research questions that were initially posed. Additionally, by employing an industrial case study that necessitated the integration of diverse wearables, the framework's capabilities were effectively showcased. The data collected within the context of this use case facilitated the exploration of the second research question, as it allowed for the application of data transformations, highlighting the substantial impact of fatigue on the worker's mobility speed.

While further research is necessary, including additional use cases and more extensive and long-term worker monitoring, to establish the sustainability of the chosen key performance indicator (KPI) and explore the potential of additional KPIs, the results collected thus far are promising and hold significant value. The integration among various stakeholders involved in the analysis of the process helps reduce the presence of unknown factors and their effects. This is particularly crucial when considering the enhancement of the quality of other modeling techniques that begin with such datasets.

This framework facilitates a seamless integration between human-related data flows and machinery-related data flows, thereby structurally supporting the advancement of the Industry 5.0 concept.

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